

Language Learning Strategies in Filipino and Preference For Oral Communication as Predictors of Students' Anxiety in Oral Language

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to identify the relationship between language learning strategies and students' preferences in oral communication as predictors of anxiety in oral language among students. The (310) participants are from Davao City. This is a quantitative study that utilized a descriptive correlational survey. In analyzing the data, mean, Pearson r, and multiple regression were used. As a result of this research, it was found that the descriptive level of participants in language learning strategies is high, indicating that students often demonstrate their use. Similarly, in terms of preference for oral communication, it only obtained a moderate level, meaning that students only occasionally demonstrate their preference for oral communication. Furthermore, anxiety in oral language also obtained a high level. The results also revealed that there is no significant relationship between language learning strategy and anxiety in oral language among students. There is also a significant negative relationship between students' preference for oral communication and anxiety in oral language. Emotional, cognitive, compensation, social strategy, and teacher-student communication strategies are predictors with the most significant influence on students' anxiety in oral language. This study helps teachers, especially with students, to have appropriate language learning strategies and use them for preference in oral communication as predictors in oral language.

Keywords: education, oral communication, students, language learning strategies, preference for oral communication, predictors of oral language, quantitative descriptive correlational survey, stratified random sampling, Davao City

I. INTRODUCTION

Students' anxiety when speaking in front of the class is one of their issues. Disturbing factors include worry about possible mistakes or comments from their fellow classmates (Zhou et. al., p. 1). Students often experience anxiety in oral language, even in its early stages of development, as a result of inadequate instruction and even remarks from teachers when they make mistakes (Chen at Hwang, p.1619). When someone is speaking orally, anxiety might arise if they are unsure of what will happen next, anticipating a bad outcome specially if they are terrified of the circumstance the student is in.

There is no doubt that speech anxiety impairs performance. If so, it would be preferable to stay away from such work due to the high levels of anxiety and stress involved (Hidayoza p. 8). Self-confidence is significantly impacted by student anxiety. When spoken language is not adequately developed, students frequently struggle. Numerous investigations have identified this issue. It was stated on page 91 of Marlon's study that some children at a Philippine school are genuinely experiencing nervousness when speaking. The majority of them experience anxiety, particularly during speaking-focused practice.

According to Krashen's affective filter hypothesis, anxious students find it difficult to acquire a language because they are less motivated to participate in oral communication activities. Kalra and Siribud pointed out on page 195 that, in line with this context, it is really concerning because a lot of students are actually impacted by it. Anxiety can affect spoken language in a variety of ways, including fear, shyness, low self-esteem, and even forgetting what to say next.

The anxiety has a broad impact on many parts of a person's life, that's why, the study of anxiety in spoken language is crucial. Additionally, it serves as essential for advancing the field of language education, enhancing students' linguistic proficiency, fostering psychological health, and cultivating proficient communication abilities.

Research on speech anxiety will lead to the development of evidence-based instructional strategies and interventions. According to Bashori et. al., p. 1058, of the four language skills, spoken language is the most stressful skill. If so, it deserves attention.

A more thorough knowledge of the connection between language learning techniques and spoken language anxiety is required. Finding the elements that can assist in reducing a student's spoken language anxiety is also crucial for meaningful and successful language acquisition. Chow et al.'s research (p.719) indicates that students typically employ direct tactics, such as metacognitive and social strategies, when learning a language. Additionally, Sethy (p. 39) provided support for the idea that employing methods helped students engage in active learning, prevent mistakes, and boost their confidence—especially in higher education settings.

Any of the many techniques students employ to acquire and advance their language abilities is referred to as a language learning strategy. It is mentioned in the study by Napil and San Jose on page 152 that students in the Philippines employ methods, particularly while developing oral language in the classroom. In this regard, it was discovered that their anxiety stems from their fear of communicating, which is caused by their lack of learned language. Hakim and Suniar (p. 125) state that utilizing socio-affective techniques in interactions between peers and teachers might lessen fear and increase a preference for oral communication. Nonetheless, proficient language learners know which approach to use, and it all depends on the preferred learning method.

However, it has been observed that students' preferences for oral communication are significantly influenced by their fear when speaking (Sutarsyah, p. 145). Regarding oral communication preferences, Shanti Manipuspika (p. 200) also mentioned that friends and fellow students have a bigger influence than strangers for students who struggle with spoken language fear. It was also found in Nkrumah's study (p.51) that anxiety influences students' preferences for oral communication and language acquisition. This demonstrates how students express anxiety and worry about choosing oral communication over written communication. They believe they are prone to making mistakes, which makes them more nervous when speaking. Manipuspika (p.200) added that it is important to take into account the fact that students' preferences for oral communication vary depending on their individual behaviors.

McCroskey's Communication Apprehension Theory serves as the foundation for this study. This idea states that people who experience severe anxiety when speaking to others are more likely to become disinterested in spoken language. Even if one's proficiency or preference in oral communication increases, the likelihood of learning more languages is reduced. Anxiety can be controlled in a communicative setting when learning a language by using techniques like practicing, keeping track of one's own development, and taking criticism. Furthermore, a preference for oral communication motivates students to engage in talks as a coping mechanism for their anxiety.

The strategic competence model developed by Canale and Swain supported this. It says that developing strategic competency is emphasized as a crucial component of learning a language. The ability of a student to employ suitable language learning strategies in various communication circumstances is referred to as strategic competence, as articulated by Canale and Swain. According to this, students who are good at using methods tend to be less anxious when speaking in public. Furthermore, linguistic proficiency and other linguistic qualities are required for good public speaking since they are undoubtedly utilized in spoken language.

The theory of McCroskey and Baer's Willingness to Communicate is connected to the previously discussed. Based on the idea that people have the freedom to communicate or not, it was designed to ascertain if a person chooses to do so in specific situations. It also describes how each person is prepared to converse in a second language. It reduces nervousness when speaking. Students who employ effective strategies, such as guidelines, goal-setting, and efficacy, are more likely to favor oral communication over written communication and to experience less oral language anxiety. This is particularly crucial when it comes to language acquisition. Additionally, language learners who have a strong preference for speaking aloud may also actively look for chances to participate in conversations in which they are encouraged to speak. As a result, it produces better overall learning outcomes and enhances oral language skills (Bećirović et al., p. 96).

The following variables will be used in this research to address the study's problem. The following include students oral language anxiety, oral communication preferences, and language learning strategies. Students who employ these techniques have higher language learning outcomes than those who do not take these strategies into account. In order to be more effective in meeting the needs of the students, teachers must possess the necessary skills and experience in selecting and implementing established ways for teaching and using spoken language (Marinkovic & Pesic, p. 221).

Using Oxford's Strategy Inventory of Language Learning (SILL) to Assess the Strategy Use of a Group of First and Third Year EFL Algerian University Students is a study by Nesrine Aoudjit Bessai that focuses on six factors. The affective strategy is the first indicator. Emotion, attitude, and even the student's motivation which plays a significant role in the student's language learning are all included in the affective strategy. The cognitive strategy is the second indicator.

Cognitive strategy includes reasoning, analyzing, taking notes, organizing newly learned words, connecting previously taught words to newly learned ones, and even deducing a word's meaning from its context.

Next is the compensation strategy. This allows students to use, although in limited amounts, the new language they have learned. The metacognitive technique is also covered, which focuses on goal-setting, planning, and self-management in connection to the language learned. In addition to the ones just listed, a social approach exists. In addition to practicing the language that will be used, the learner using this technique may have the chance to speak with someone who speaks the target language or ask questions in order to receive clarification. The memory strategy comes last. There is a focus on using mnemonic devices, flashcards, and even similarity recognition to help with word memorization.

Also in the research of Elaheh Tavakoli and Mohammad Davoudi titled *Willingness to Communicate Orally: The Case of Iranian EFL Learners*, three indicators were mentioned, and they are as follows; preference for communicating with teachers and students, especially in classroom activities; preference for communicating with classmates and friends, such as, for example, if there are group activities; and lastly, preference for communicating with foreigners or strangers, especially when they have questions.

The last variable is the student's anxiety when speaking. In his research, Abdalaziz M. Toubot highlighted the challenges that cause students to feel uneasy when speaking in public. The first is communication apprehension. Students stay away from social anxiety and shame. The second is the fear of negative judgement. The students' attempt to restrict their engagement in communication was a direct result of their fear of possible criticism. Low self-confidence comes last. Low self-esteem is reported to prevent people from practicing their target language due to their fear of making mistakes and believing that doing so will simply make them look ridiculous (Leong & Ahmadi, 34).

The relationships between the concepts used in this study are shown in the diagram below. It is divided into two concepts. The preference for oral communication and the language learning strategy that serve as independent variables in this study. It will be determined which predictor has the most influence on the student's anxiety in oral language, which is an independent variable.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

This conceptual framework shows the relationship between Language Learning Strategy, Preference for oral communication of Students, and Students' Anxiety in Oral Language.

There is some research that can be read on the internet regarding language learning strategies, student preferences in oral communication, even student anxiety in oral language. In this research, the relationship between language learning strategy, student preference in oral communication and the student's perceived anxiety in oral language will be focused. It will be examined what kind of strategy is appropriate for the development of the student's preference in oral communication that can relieve the student's anxiety in the oral language. It is important to immediately determine the appropriate strategy for this, especially in the current era where students are facing anxiety in spoken language due to their lack of desire in oral communication. Any result can be applied immediately by the teacher and student in relation to said research.

This study is to describe the level of use of language learning strategies and student preferences in oral communication as a predictor of oral language anxiety. The objectives that follow will be attained by the study: first, describe the level of language learning strategies according to cognitive, affective, compensatory, metacognitive, social, and memory strategies. Second, determine the level of preference for oral communication depending on the following factors: willingness to communicate with foreigners or strangers, inclination for speaking with teachers and fellow students, and willingness to communicate with friends and classmates. Third, assess the student's level of anxiety when speaking in public in terms of low self-confidence, communication apprehension, and fear of negative judgment. Fourth, is there a significant relationship between students' spoken language anxiety and their language learning strategy. Fifth, is there a connection between oral language anxiety and students' preferences for oral communication. Lastly, what domain has the biggest impact on students' fear when speaking.

This research is significant since it is undeniable that oral communication skills are crucial in every setting, profession, and circumstance. This study will also assist the Department of Education in determining the causes regarding the students oral language anxiety. In educational system, notably in the Philippines, which needs a well-designed curriculum to improve student achievement, particularly in the area of spoken language development. The findings of this study also have the potential to enhance the degree of language learning strategies and preferences in oral communication as a predictor of student anxiety in spoken language, which makes it relevant for both teachers and students. Modern graduates also need to be able to compete globally. Speaking is one of the most important skills in any setting, so they must be proficient in it. Consequently, this research plays a significant part in influencing students' communication skills.

The researcher will benefit from this research in meeting the requirements for the MAEd-Filipino degree. The study's findings will be useful in determining if oral communication preference and language acquisition approach actually correlate to predict oral language anxiety. In conclusion, this study holds significance as a foundation for future research endeavors aimed at expanding knowledge of communication abilities.

II. METHODS

Participants of the Study

The research was conducted in three private universities here in the City of Davao, Davao del Sur, Region XI and the researcher used stratified random sampling to determine the number of each respondent who will answer the questionnaire in which the population is divided into subgroups that called "strata" (Nguyen, 1).

According to Cochran p.64, random sampling is the process of choosing in such a way that all the identified population has equal and free choice to be a participant and Cresswell also supported it in the same definition. The selected students of schools A, B and C will be the participants in this study for the 2023-2024 school year with a total number of 1390 and have a Filipino subject. Using stratified random sampling, 310 participants were obtained from it. According to Memon (1) this number is suitable for this research.

The criteria to be a respondent are as follows: they must be students of the said school, they must be enrolled in the high school department with GAS, HUMSS, ABM, and STEM strands with Filipino subject so that it is fully valid and credible. Students in the said school who do not have a Filipino subject are not invited to be respondents in this study. In unforeseen circumstances and reasons, the respondent may withdraw as a participant in said research. It is only necessary to inform the researcher. Respondents who do not want to answer the questionnaire provided by the researcher will not be forced. Each respondent has freedom of choice.

Instrument of the study

The questionnaire that will be used in this research is divided into three parts. The first part is about language learning strategies. This questionnaire was a guide and derived from Nesrine Aoudjit Bessai's study titled Using Oxford's Strategy Inventory of Language Learning (SILL) to Assess the Strategy Use of a Group of First and Third Year EFL Algerian University Students. It has six (6) indicators, as follows: emotional strategy, cognitive strategy, compensatory strategy, metacognitive strategy, social strategy, and memory strategy. It has a total number of items in all indicators of fifty (50).

The second part is about another independent variable, the student's preference for oral communication, derived from the study questionnaire by Elaheh Tavakoli and Mohammad Davoudi titled Willingness to Communicate Orally: The Case of Iranian EFL Learners. The questionnaire consists of three (3) indicators. These are preferences for communicating with teachers and students, preferences for communicating with classmates and friends, and preferences for communicating with foreigners. It has a total of twenty-eight (28) items in all indicators.

Lastly, the student's anxiety in the spoken language is derived from the questionnaire of the study by Abdalaziz M. Toubot et al. entitled "Examining Levels and Factors of Speaking Anxiety among EFL Libyan English Undergraduate Students" in their Foreign Language Speaking Anxiety Scale, or FLSAS. It has three indicators and a total of items on all indicators that are sixteen (16). Indicators such as communication apprehension, fear of negative judgment, and low self-confidence.

In the pilot testing of the questionnaires, it appeared from the Cronbach's alpha result that the questionnaires on language learning strategy, oral communication preference, and oral language anxiety scored higher than 0.70. That is, they are acceptable, which signaled the use of questionnaires in gathering data. For measuring the level of language learning strategy, oral communication preference and student's oral language anxiety, the researcher used the following range: 4.20-5.0 with a descriptive level that is the highest meaning that the identified item is always manifested in the above-mentioned variable, 3.40-4.19 with a descriptive level of high which means that the referred item was often manifested in the above-mentioned variable, 2.60-3.39 with a descriptive level of medium because the referred item was manifested only once in mentioned variable and 1.80-2.59 with a descriptive level of low, meaning that the referred item is rarely manifested in the mentioned variable and 1.00-1.79 with a descriptive level of the lowest meaning that it is not manifested in the mentioned variable.

Design and Methods

This research was conducted based on a quantitative descriptive-correlational survey. The descriptive correlational survey is designed to describe the relationship between each variable. According to Panda (1), the descriptive correlation design describes the relationship and level of each variable, and it is also best for gathering data. In answering the questionnaire, the maximum scale is 5, which means that the student agrees most in all cases. 1 is the lowest, which means strongly disagreeing in all cases.

The researcher followed all the criteria to carry out the study. To be sure, here is the following step taken by the researcher: From the adapted questionnaire that was analyzed, translated, and validated by the researcher to the evaluators. After being validated and revised by the researcher by correcting and adjusting the validators, the researcher prepared it for formal validation. The researcher also hired an external validator to further increase the credibility of the instrument used. The researcher arranged all the validation requirements for U MERC, waited for any comments and corrections, and then sent them back to U MERC for final validation. After the initial review by U MERC, the researcher was authorized to conduct the study. The researcher was given a certificate numbered U MERC 2023-435.

The researcher asked for permission by doing everything for the head of the university so that this letter will give strength to the permission letter that will be given to the chosen school. The letter must be approved by the dean's advisor of the graduate institution of the professional program and the researcher's advisor. The researcher compressed the letter for formal consent to the heads of universities A, B, and C where the study will be conducted and showed it to the selected Filipino teacher. The letter was adopted to allow the students to answer the questionnaires.

After the questionnaire was administered, the researcher obtained the results of the pilot testing and interpreted them by his chosen statistician. After getting a result from the selected statistician, a signal was given to begin formal data collection. The researcher set aside one day in each school for the students to answer it. He made his participants fully understand the guide to answering his questionnaire, and no coercion or intimidation occurred. After gathering the required data for the study, the statistician interpreted the final data. Answers were analyzed and interpreted for successful research using mean, Pearson r , and multiple regression. The researcher gave his discussion, conclusion, and even his recommendation as a result of the results of the study. Listed below are statistics used to meet the goals listed.

The following statistics were used in this study: **mean**, because this method can describe the relationship between language learning strategies, the student's preference for oral communication, and anxiety in oral language. **Pearson r**: in determining if there is a significant relationship between language learning strategy and oral language anxiety, student preference for oral communication and oral language anxiety. Meanwhile, **multiple regression** was used to measure the p value of the independent variable to find out which predictor has a significant relationship with the independent variable.

In conducting this research, the ethical consideration and safety of each participant are in the mind of the researcher. The researcher will preserve the credibility of the respondent's names, and the researcher will endeavor to keep the data confidential in accordance with the Data Privacy Law.

The participant is free to include their names in answering the questions. The researcher informed the respondents that whatever results are obtained from this study will remain confidential, and the personal information of the institution and respondents related to this study will be kept private.

Apart from the consent form to be signed by the participants in the study, the researcher will also allocate a consent form for the teachers and counselors of each school that will participate in the study. The researcher also explained the potential benefits of any outcome of the study. There is also a formal letter for the president of the institution that prepared the researcher, and it was approved by the Dean of the Graduate Program of the Professional Schools of the University of Mindanao. The researcher requested permission to conduct the study. All signatures are valid and have gone through the verification process.

In this research, no professional judgment was made by the researcher. There is no conflict of interest between the researcher and the study participants. The researcher also did not know most of the respondents and their teachers.

As a whole, the researcher tried to understand each concept and idea of each author in each variable, and there is no trace of claiming any knowledge or idea of different authors in the said study. The researcher identified and mentioned the authors and proponents related to the said study.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Level of Language Learning Strategy

The table below shows the level of language learning strategy with the following indicators: affective strategy, cognitive strategy, compensatory strategy, metacognitive strategy, social strategy and memory strategy.

It can be seen that there is a total standard deviation of .484 and a mean score of 3.59, which describes a *high* level of ability to use language learning strategies. That is, the student often demonstrates the use of language learning strategies. In the study by Balones and Gempes (p. 78), it was seen that the result was the same, particularly at the level of language learning strategies.

Table 1

Level of Language Learning Strategy

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive level
Affective strategy	.679	3.18	Moderate
Cognitive strategy	.573	3.65	High
Compensatory strategy	.688	3.67	High
Metacognitive strategy	.712	3.65	High
Social strategy	.706	3.86	High
Memory strategy	.668	3.53	High
Total	.484	3.59	High

Among all the language learning strategy indicators in the same table, it can be seen that the social strategy obtained a standard deviation of .706 and the highest mean score of 3.86, while the emotional strategy has a standard deviation of .679. and the lowest mean score of 3.18. Students can practice speaking, even with their fellow students, to improve it. On the other hand, it is also necessary to increase the emotional strategy because it was mentioned in Sakka's study, p. 85, that through this, their anxiety will be reduced and their feelings will be stimulated while they

speak. The following table shows the level of preference in oral communication divided into three indicators. Based on this, a total standard deviation of .737 and a mean score of 3.12 were obtained. To give direction, the student has moderately or only sometimes demonstrated their preference for oral communication.

Table 2
Level of Preference for oral communication

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive level
Preference of oral communication with teachers and classmates	.622	3.28	Moderate
Preference of oral communication with classmates and friends	.931	3.19	Moderate
Preference of oral communication with strangers	.1.068	.2.90	Moderate
Total	.737	3.12	Moderate

It can be noted that the moderate level of this result indicates that students have a positive preference for oral communication. The positive relationship between teacher and student that obtained a standard deviation of .622 and a mean score of 3.28 indicates that there is an important role in the development of students' preferences for oral communication. In Mercer and Dörnyei's study, p. 1, the importance of having a positive teacher-student relationship was emphasized in order to create a supportive classroom climate and to promote the preference for oral communication and interaction. in students' academics. On the other hand, low motivation or interest in communicating with others with a standard deviation of 1.068 and a mean score of 2.90 may contribute to a decrease in preference for oral communication. In this regard, Mercer and Dörnyei, p. 1, emphasized the role of motivation in language learning contexts. It is suggested here that motivation and interest in communication positively influence preferences for oral communication.

Table 3 shows the result of the level of anxiety in spoken language. It obtained a total standard deviation of .918 and a mean score of 3.40 which means its level is high.

Table 3
Level of Student's Anxiety in oral language

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive level
Communication Apprehension	.878	3.31	Moderate
Fear of Negative evaluation	1.04	3.52	High
Low self-confidence	1.11	3.37	Moderate
Total	.918	3.40	High

Among the indicators of this variable, a standard deviation of 1.04, a high mean score of 3.52, and the fear of negative judgment were obtained. This means that fear of negative judgment has a significant impact on students' oral language anxiety. Mentioned in the study by Pang et al. al., p. 14, that the fear of negative judgment is indeed a key aspect of experienced anxiety. Furthermore, Adriatico (p. 28) also added that it is not the speaking activity that causes them anxiety but the possible negative evaluation from the listener. Because of this, their participation is affected.

On the other hand, it is shown that students also have a fear of talking. It obtained a standard deviation of .878 and a mean score of 3.31. Subekti, p. 14, noted that there is a significant negative relationship between fear of communication and communication skills. A person with good communication skills is less likely to have a fear of speaking. In Cadogan's study, p. 81, it was stated that it is appropriate to focus on the fear of talking and communication skills because they can positively influence the academic aspects of students, especially in oral language work.

Table 4

General Relationship between Language Learning Strategies, Oral Communication Preference and Students' Oral Language Anxiety Language learning strategies in Filipino Preference for Oral Communication Student's Anxiety in oral Language

	Language learning strategies in Filipino	Preference for Oral Communication	Student's Anxiety in oral Language
Language learning strategies in Filipino	1	.583** .000	0.013 .826
Preference for Oral Communication	.583** .000	1	-0.240** .000
Student's Anxiety in oral Language	0.013 .826	-0.240** .000	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 shows that there is no significant relationship between language learning strategy and student anxiety in spoken language, where there is an r-value of 0.013 and a p-value of 0.826. It can be seen that it is more than 0.05, which means that we are not rejecting the null hypothesis.

In addition, the above result shows an r value of -0.240 and a p value of less than 0.05, which rejects the null hypothesis and means that there is a significant negative relationship between student's preference for oral communication and their anxiety. oral language learners. In the study by Peng and Woodrow (p. 605), the results also showed that there is a negative relationship between the student's preference for oral communication and the student's anxiety about the oral language. This indicates that as preference for verbal communication increases, there is a high probability that anxiety will decrease. Therefore, the teacher's role in this situation is important. When students feel the teacher's support, the negative relationship between the student's preference for oral communication and the student's oral language anxiety will be stronger, and certainly the anxiety will be weakened.

Table 5

Multiple Regression showing the Influence of the Combined Indicator of Language Learning Strategy and Indicator of Student's Preference in Oral Communication on Student's Anxiety in Oral Language

Model	Coefficients a		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error			
1 (Constant)	3.289	.377		8.722	.000
Affective Strategy	.280	.084	.207	3.326	.001
Cognitive strategy	-.329	.119	-.205	-2.754	.006
Compensatory strategy	.300	.074	.225	4.038	.000
Metacognitive strategy	-.065	.106	-.051	-.616	.538
Social Strategy	.319	.087	.245	3.681	.000
Memory Strategy	-.096	.099	-.070	-.967	.334
Preference of oral communication with teachers and classmates	-.334	.130	-.226	-2.579	.010
Preference of oral communication with classmates and friends	.001	.074	.001	.016	.987
Preference of oral communication with strangers	-.084	.054	-.098	-1.557	.121
R	.468				
R2	.219				
F	9.370				
P	.000b				

Dependent Variable: Anxiety in oral language

Table 5 shows the multiple regression analysis of language learning strategy, student preference in oral communication, and student anxiety in oral language. Based on the results, it can be seen that the emotional strategy, cognitive strategy, compensation strategy, social strategy, and communication with the teacher and student towards the student's anxiety in spoken language have $R^2 = 21.9$ and $F = 9.370$. It is meant to be interpreted that the aforementioned predictors have the most significant influence on the student's anxiety in spoken language. Some indicators of language learning strategy and oral communication preference are considered, which show a significant relationship with a p-value of .000 and a multiple regression of .000 that confirms the result.

On the other hand, when the indicators of language learning strategies—emotional strategies, cognitive strategies, compensatory strategies, and social strategies—are combined with the indicator of preference in oral communication, communication with the teacher and students can help to alleviate the anxiety of the student. studies in spoken language. It has an F-ratio of 9.370 and $p (.000) < 0.05$. These indicators account for approximately 21.9% of the change that occurred in the student's anxiety in the spoken language, while 78.1% can say that factors can be associated with the student's anxiety in the spoken language other than the aforementioned indicators.

In further analysis, emotional strategy, cognitive strategy, compensatory strategy, social strategy, and communication with the teacher and student are domains that have a significant influence on student's anxiety in spoken language.

IV. Conclusion and Recommendation

From the first objective of the study, which states what the level of language learning strategy is, the researcher found from the participants of the study that it got a descriptive interpretation that was high. That is, the student often demonstrates the use of strategies related to language learning. In the second objective that measures the level of the student's preference for oral communication, it got a descriptive interpretation that the student showed moderate or only sometimes their preference for oral communication. The third objective refers to the measurement of the student's level of anxiety in the spoken language, and it got a high description, which just means that anxiety in the spoken language is also often seen in the students.

It has also been found that there is no significant relationship between language learning strategy and student anxiety in spoken language. On the other hand, the result of student preference in oral communication and student anxiety in oral language has a significant negative relationship. Finally, emotional strategy, cognitive strategy, compensatory strategy, social strategy, and communication with the teacher and student are domains that have a significant influence on student anxiety in spoken language.

In the theory mentioned by the researcher, Canale and Swain's Strategic Competence, which describes the ability of a student to apply proper language learning strategies in different communication situations, the results of the research were contradictory. this. Based on the result, language learning strategy has no significant relationship with student's anxiety in spoken language. On the other hand, the significant negative relationship between preference for oral communication and student anxiety means that students may also lose preference for oral communication when they are anxious for oral language or vice versa, as noted by McCroskey in his Communication Apprehension Theory.

In the findings of the researcher's study of language learning strategies and the student's preference for oral communication as a predictor of oral language, the researcher recommends the following:

First, teachers need to create a supportive and inclusive classroom environment. Pay attention to valuing students' emotions and encourage them to freely express their thoughts and feelings. This can be achieved by fostering open communication, actively listening to students' concerns, and showing empathy for their emotional experiences. Through this, students will feel valued and understood, and this will improve their motivation to engage in activities related to learning.

Second, in order to increase the preference for oral communication in different contexts, the development of a supportive and inclusive classroom or social environment is very important. Teachers play an important role in creating an environment where students feel valued, respected, and encouraged to express themselves. This can be achieved through active listening, providing constructive feedback, and showing respect for students' opinions and contributions, which increases confidence and preference in oral communication.

Third, it is important to use strategies to increase self-confidence and eventually overcome the fear of spoken language. Creating a supportive and non-judgmental environment is important. This helps students express themselves without fear of negative judgment.

Lastly, for future researchers, delve deeper into exploring additional factors that may influence students' anxiety in spoken language contexts, such as language proficiency levels, cultural experiences, or in dynamic classroom situations.

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